

Selective Entropy Based on Measurement, Conjugate Variables and Quantum Numbers

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In classical mechanics, one assumes one may measure precise momentum and x positions. One may argue, however, that a measurement involves changing the momentum of a particle (i.e. an impulse hit) and that such a change does not occur either in an instant of time or at a point x . For example, a classical particle in a potential $V(x)$ changes its velocity in a region dx , but at the same time is said to have a velocity of $v(x)$ to leading order as dx shrinks to zero. One may argue that dx does not shrink to zero and may not be tiny with respect to an overall length scale. Given that an interaction involves a particle and a potential or another particle, one may argue that a finite dx should be associated with both. Thus a particle with constant momentum should have a tiny dx associated with it, possibly a function of p , but at the same time there is a constant probability for a measurement to take place at any x point. Thus we argue that there are two sets of probability schemes, one for dx and another for a larger length scale and constant probability. This should point to two entropy schemes, each associated with the type of measurement done and its analysis. For example, a two slit system may be used to measure the interaction probability. This gives rise to an interference probability. At the same time, many two slit system may be used to measure the center of mass position of the particle, ignoring the interference pattern. This gives rise to $P(x)=1/L$ and a completely different Shannon's entropy.

Given that there is a dx probability scheme for a constant p associated with interactions, an associated entropy should appear when such an interaction occurs, but this now involves breaking the constant p and considering the associated dx probabilities. Thus there is both momentum and spatial entropy combined as in two slit interference.

In the case of a bound state, there are numerous $\exp(ipx)$ eigenstates (due to interactions with $V(x)$), suggesting both internal p and x entropies, but overall one has a single energy eigenstate. In terms of energy one has a fixed state (although $\exp(-iE_n t)$ suggests there are frequency pockets in time pointing towards a kind of time entropy. If one considers only interactions which change a particle from one E_n to another, a particle in a single state at $T=\text{temperature}=0$ has entropy 0 (even though the state itself has momentum and spatial entropy). Thus it seems entropy is selective depending on the type of interactions present and what eigenvalues they change.

In other words, classically one counts states when computing entropy, but in quantum mechanics one may count states by defining states in terms of quantum numbers. One may consider a bound state to be a single certain state with eigenvalue E_n and consider entropy being created if interactions (photon/phonon absorption/emission) break the single E_n . In such a case, one may ignore the breaking of $\exp(ipx)$ s within a bound state which implies momentum entropy as well as the spatial entropy linked with even a single $\exp(ipx)$. In other words, one may select various different kinds of probabilities linked with different eigenvalues and their measurements when calculating Shannon's entropy.

Entropy and Measurement

Consider a particle with constant momentum which may be measured within a spatial length L . Such a particle has constant velocity and its momentum represents the physical impulse it may impart during a collision i.e. measurement. A measurement may be complicated and not take place at an instant in time or point x . If one has an ensemble of constant p single particles, however, (with no clock present), the center-of-mass, so to speak, of a measurement may take place at any x point, as there is no preferred x . Thus p (momentum) is certain, but there is a probability $P(x)=1/L$ related to position leading to a Shannon's entropy:

Spatial Shannon's entropy at each x : $1/L \ln(1/L)$ ((1))

As noted, a measurement may not take place at an instant in time at a point x . In such a case, one might argue that it occurs within dx , but this dx should be associated both with the particle p and with the measuring object ($V(x)$, photon, particle etc) because according to Newton, there is action-reaction. Does dx switch on only when an interaction occurs, or is it a property of a particle with constant momentum? We argue it should be a complementary property of a particle with momentum p . This idea, however, seems to contradict the notion of the particle having the same probability to be at any x point. Furthermore, dx must somehow be manifested physically. Given that one thinks of constant v motion in terms of probabilities i.e. a constant probability to be at any x point within L , we argue one may think in terms of probabilities associated within dx . Thus:

- (A) A particle with constant momentum carries with it a dx length associated with interaction. There should be a spatial probability associated with dx and hence also an entropy. At the same time the dx probability should map to a probability of $1/L$ for the particle to be at any x point, which leads to a different entropy. Why are there two entropies? One entropy is associated with a specific interaction region and not the cm position of the particle in a larger region of space. In classical physics, one ignores the interaction region entropy and is only concerned with the entropy in the larger spatial region. Thus measurements don't affect the entropy classically (i.e. one may determine p and x as points.)
- (B) A particle with constant p carries a dx and so has an entropy associated with this dx , even though p is constant i.e. there is no momentum entropy. If an interaction occurs, however, the p vector should change and so during the interaction there may be both a p entropy and dx entropy. These may combine to yield a specific x pattern such as that produced by a two slit experiment. The magnitude of p does not change, but one considers different p directions i.e. $\exp(i p_1 \cdot r)$ and $\exp(i p_2 \cdot r)$ such that $\|p_1\|=\|p_2\|$.

Calculating the Intrinsic Spatial Entropy Associated With a Constant Momentum

We argue above that a constant momentum particle is associated with an intrinsic dx . Furthermore, this dx is associated with an x -probability scheme, but at the same time must map to a probability in which each x point has the same probability i.e. $P(x)=\text{constant}$. $P(x)=\text{constant}$ holds for any p , but it is suggested there should exist a $P1(p,x)$ which differs for different p 's as each p yields a different impulse hit. $P1(p,x)$ is an interaction type of probability which maps to a constant.

If $P1(p,x)$ is a probability associated with an impulse p , then:

$P1(-p,x)P1(p,x) = \text{probability for no impulse which should be the same as } P(x)=\text{constant} \quad ((2))$

We suggest: $P1(p,x)=P1(px)$ based on the action $-Et+px$ form and then note that $((2))$ implies:

$P1(px) = \exp(ipx) \quad ((4))$ if one does not want the probability to grow or diminish infinitely.

Thus a constant p is associated with probability pockets $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ and we suggest that there is an intrinsic entropy i.e.

$Pa(px) = |\cos(px)| C$ within a half-wavelength where C is a constant $((5))$

It seems, however, that one does measure $\exp(ipx)$ unless an interaction occurs. In such a case, it may not be the pure $\exp(ipx)$ that one measures, but a sum of $a(p1)\exp(ip1x) + a(p2)\exp(ip2x)$ etc as in the two slit experiment. In such a case, a spatial probability arises due to the spatial $\cos(px)$, $\sin(px)$ pieces as well as the different p values (created by the interaction). Such a probability would then be used in a Shannon's entropy calculation. Thus it seems that the interaction/measurement governs the probability which emerges and hence the entropy.

Quantum Bound State

A quantum bound state may be described by a potential $V(x)$ creating various $\exp(ipx)$'s. If one averages these, there is both momentum and spatial entropy. $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$ leads to a spatial probability of $W^*(x)W(x)$ ($W^*=W$ for a bound case), which may be used in Shannon's entropy, but this is really a combination of both momentum and spatial entropy as each $\exp(ipx)$ carries with it its own spatial entropy based on a probability of $C|\cos(px)|$ within half a wavelength. $a^*(p)a(p)$ is the probability to find (i.e. measure) a particle in a state with momentum p , but with no x information. This is usually then used to create a momentum entropy:

$$- a^*(p)a(p) \ln\{ a^*(p)a(p) \} \quad ((2))$$

, but we argue there should be a spatial entropy as well because one has no information about where the particle is, i.e. a constant $P(x)=1/L$ where L is an estimated length related to the length between the classical turning points and some portion outside, depending perhaps on a cutoff value for $W(x)W(x)$.

Thus in the bound case, one has two entropies:

$-W \ln\{W\}$ ((3)) and ((2)) with the added $-1/L \ln(1/L)$

How does one interpret these two? ((2)) with the extra spatial piece is an entropy similar to the classical entropy i.e. one considers probabilities of p and the particle may be spatially anywhere within L . Entropy ((3)), on the other hand, is an interaction type of entropy which arises due to the intrinsic spatial probability linked with $\exp(ipx)$, which is now averaged with other $\exp(ipx)$ s with weights $a(p)$ before creating an overall $W(x)W(x)$ as in the two slit experiment. It has an appearance of a spatial entropy, but includes the effects of differing momenta.

Thus, just as with a constant momentum particle measurable within a region L , there are two entropy schemes, one linked to the region itself and another to dx associated with a constant p .

It seems, however, that there is still another entropy scheme. A single eigenfunction has an energy E_n . If one counts states based on the energy value, then if a particle is in an energy eigenstate, one may argue it has zero entropy as its state is known e.g. at $T=\text{temperature}=0$. Intrinsically, however, we have argued that there are two different entropy schemes associated with the bound state. Thus entropy seems to be selective. Within a bound state, one uses the eigenvalue p (which is not constant) to analyze entropy as interactions occur between the single particle and the potential $V(x)$. Interactions (measurements) define the entropy, but also the quantum number selected i.e. p momentum. In the case of energy eigenstates, one may consider completely different interactions which move a particle from one energy to another i.e. photon/phonon absorption/emission. In such a situation, only E_n characterizes a state and one may consider $P(E_n/T)$ and calculate entropy based on this using Shannon's entropy recipe $-\sum \text{over } n P(E_n) \ln(P(E_n))$. Thus entropy seems to be selective i.e. it may be calculated based on which quantum number one considers to be changed due to an interaction and the measurement scheme in place.

It should be noted, however, that whether one uses p as the quantum number or E_n , there is an associated spatial entropy due to the $\cos(px)$ probabilities associated with $\exp(ipx)$ and $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ associated with each E_n state. Furthermore each E_n state has an entropy due to $a^*(p)a(p)$ and $P(x)=1/L$, although these are usually not measured and so perhaps this latter entropy only applies to a scenario in which one knocks out single particles from a bound state and measures p values. Similarly, an entropy based on $W(x)W(x)$ perhaps only pertains to the case in which one is able to measure spatial density. If one measures neither p nor spatial density, but only E_n , then perhaps an entropy based on $P(E_n)$ suffices.

Thus it seems that entropy is selective, based on the kind of interactions present and their associated measurement. I.e. photon emission/absorption measure E_n values, not p or x values.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems that probabilities define Shannon's entropy - $\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$ where i is a quantum number or observable. An observable, however, is the result of a measurement, so it is the measurement and its interpretation which seem to give rise to probability and its corresponding Shannon's entropy. For example, consider a particle with constant p (momentum). One may have an ensemble of such particles with measurements occurring within a section of space L long. The measurements may be complicated and may occur over a dt and dx , but one may assign a center-of-mass to each. Thus one may consider $P(x)$ within L for all x points and find that $P(x)=1/L$. This approach which is classical ignores uncertainties within the measurement region.

In particular, we argue that an interaction involves both the particle with constant p and the measuring device ($V(x)$, photon/phonon, another particle etc). If a dx is involved, we argue the constant p particle should be associated with a dx length, whether it is interacting or not. We argue above, using the notion of impulse, that there should be an interaction probability of $\exp(ipx)$. This is very different from $1/L$, but $\exp(ipx)$ maps into a constant through $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$. I.e. one removes the impulse to find $P(x)=\text{constant}$.

If one focuses on the measurement, there is an entropy associated with it which depends on the spatial $\exp(ipx)$ as well as changes to p which occur during the interaction. For a two-slit experiment, one has a combined probability (for both slits) of $\exp(ip_1 \cdot r) + \exp(ip_2 \cdot r)$ with $\|p_1\|=\|p_2\|$. W^*W yields a spatial/momentum combined probability which yields an entropy based on this measurement.

A different measurement which uses many two slit systems placed throughout a region L to detect a particle, but ignores the interference pattern, yields $P(x)=1/L$ because the particle may interact with a two slit system placed with its center of mass anywhere with the same probability. Thus the measurement and its analysis seems to determine which probability and hence corresponding Shannon's entropy applies.

In the case of a quantum bound state, one creates the ensemble $W(x)=\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. $a^*(p)a(p)$ represents the probability to find a particle in a state p with no information about x , but this corresponds to a specific type of measurement. We assign a momentum probability of $a(p)a(p)$ and a spatial one of $1/L$ to this type of measurement where L is an estimated length (distance between classical turning points plus some length outside based on a cutoff of $W(x)W(x)$). This yields a certain entropy.

Alternatively, $W(x)W(x)$ describes a spatial density and if one measures it, one has an entropy linked with $W(x)W(x) \ln\{WW\}$ which incorporates different p values and their associated spatial pieces $\exp(ipx)$.

Overall, however, one has an energy eigenstate and one may not measure either p or x probabilities. Instead one may measure probabilities for a particle to be in E_n i.e. $P(E_n/T)$ where the interaction is the absorption/emission of photons/phonons. This leads to a Shannon's entropy based on this probability.

Thus entropy seems to be linked to the type of measurement done and what quantum number or value is measured.